

PROVIDING EFFECTIVE WORK ON THE CARDINAL ROOT

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Abstract: The long-known conservation methods include increasing the shelf life of products by drying them. There are several drying methods, each of which has its advantages. Special requirements are imposed on the drying of food products and raw materials.

This article analyzes the change in glycyrrhizin content after drying licorice roots, which are raw materials for the food and pharmaceutical industry, according to various signs. According to the results of the analysis, the duration of the process with microwave drying of raw materials was 80 minutes per 200 g, with drying using IR rays - 240 minutes (4 hours). According to HPLC analysis, it was found that the content of glycerizin in licorice was more preserved during microwave drying.

Key words: drying, licorice, microwave drying, infrared rays, glycyrrhizin, moisture, mold, dry matter.

Entry. The drying process is a complex process that involves heat and condensation. Drying is carried out for different purposes in various fields of chemistry, food, pharmaceuticals, construction, textiles, and public housing.

The purpose of desiccation of agricultural raw materials and foodstuffs, in other words, is to stop the biological processes in their composition, thereby extending their shelf life, reducing the costs of storage and transportation, increasing the concentration of useful components in their composition.

The moisture content of raw materials and products leads to the decrease of useful components, accelerating the biochemical reactions in them, without creating the necessary environment for the activity and growth of microorganisms that lead to their degradation. In order to avoid confusion and to give the product a special specific taste, the moisture content of raw materials and products is dried using natural and artificial methods.

Food additives play a major role in the production of food, and are used to improve the color, taste, aroma, consistency, and shelf life of food. In the food industry, red pepper is used as a flavor enhancer. Red clover (or "солодка" in Russian) is one of the oldest medicinal plants known to mankind. In Chinese medicine, the medicinal properties of the radish were discovered as early as the 3rd millennium BC, and it has been used successfully as a medicine, and is still used today.

In the food industry, it is used in coffee, cocoa, marinades, compotes, jellies, flour products, holba, caramel, saffron and chocolate, as well as in the processing of fish, salted cabbage, apples and bruschetta, as a flavoring additive, as a tea additive, in Japan - as a food antioxidant additive, and in Japan and Egypt - as additives with bactericidal and fungicidal properties for food and beverages[4,5].

Licorice root extract is a unique and highly versatile substance containing a large complex of biologically active compounds, many of which have been studied as independent substances, and most of which are currently used in combination.

Glycyrrhiza glabra extract is extracted from the root of the plant. Red clover extract has anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antiviral, restorative and protective effects due to the presence of essential oils, glycosides and flavonoids.

It is proposed to use extract of red currant in the technology of baking, regulate the quality of bread products and improve their microbiological purity. The addition of licorice root and its extract to bread and bakery products prevents potato disease, which is caused by the bactericidal and fungicidal properties that resist the growth of these bacteria. The work uses generally accepted and specialized chemical, physical-chemical, organoleptic methods for studying the properties of raw materials, finished products [4].

After the roots are collected from the soil, they are thoroughly washed with water to remove soil residue. The washed-cleaned roots are well dried to a moisture content of 8% before being sent to production plants. If the raw material is not properly dried, it can become moldy, and if it is stored for a long time, it can turn brown, produce an unpleasant odor and become unusable (Picture-1).

a)

b)

c)

1st picture. Figure 1 Changes while maintaining cherry root:

a) condition after removal and storage in a cool place for 5 days;

b) washed and stored at room temperature for 5 days;

c) washed and dried to 50% humidity, condition after 7 days.

This results in a decrease in the quality of the raw material, leading to a breakdown of its useful components.

There are several ways to extend the shelf life of food raw materials, materials and products, i.e. to conserve them, which differ from each other in different properties. One of the simplest and most reliable ways to extend the shelf life of food raw materials and products is the drying process. The moisture content of these products plays a key role in the development and

proliferation of microorganisms, which can lead to rapid degradation of the product. During the drying process, the moisture in them is removed by various methods, thus preventing the breakdown of useful components in the composition of raw materials and food, stopping the activity of microorganisms that lead to their deterioration[3].

Drying itself is divided into two types, natural and artificial. The advantages of artificial drying over natural drying are the ability to control the temperature, short duration of the process, high efficiency, continuous operation, and the possibility of obtaining a high quality product. There are several methods of drying, which differ from each other by different parameters (type of energy, methods of energy transfer, etc.).

Depending on the type of energy and the method of transmission, there are conductive, contact, radiation, dielectric, sublimation drying methods [2].

Drying is the most convenient and cost-effective method of preserving red algae, and is currently carried out in a variety of drying facilities, relying on a variety of drying methods. Given that the roots are harvested in autumn, when there is less sunlight and heat, they are less likely to dry naturally, which means they take longer to dry. Therefore, the roots are artificially implanted only with the help of special devices[3].

The thoroughly washed and cleaned roots were cut into small pieces and 5 g of the roots were weighed using a scale to determine the moisture content, and the moisture content was measured using the Moisture Analyzer MA110-3H-T. The humidity in the experimental carrot root was 51.69% (Picture 2).

2nd Picture. Determining the moisture content of cinnamon root.

3rd Picture. Measure the weight of the raw material for the sample on a scale.

A sample of 200 grams of sugarcane roots was extracted from the coconut tree, divided into 2-2.5 cm thick pieces, using a sample scale. Sample 1 was dried in an infrared dryer for more than 4 hours at 65 - 70°C until 20% moisture remained. The change in mass (in terms of humidity) of the sample was determined by weighing it every hour using a scale.

Experiments were conducted with two drying units running in parallel. A 200 g sample of roots taken with a scale was processed in a 2 microwave dryer in a discrete mode at 60-62°C. The microwave temperature drying process was controlled by the on-off mode using a model calculation program [6]. When the temperature of the sample reached 60 °C, the power supply was

stopped and the temperature of the sample in the microwave chamber was measured using a thermometer and then measured using a mass scale. When the temperature of the sample dropped to 40° C, the energy transfer was resumed. This is how microwave drying was done in a discrete mode.

Table-1

No	The initial mass, g	The time it takes to give the energy, s	the temperature, °C	Mass after drying, g.	The time to cool, s	Mass after cooling, g
1.	200	30	60	198	117	196,7
2.	196,7	30	57	195,6	122	193,1
3.	193,1	35	62	191,3	165	187,4
4.	187,4	25	62	185,8	198	182,7
5.	182,7	25	61	178,8	220	176
6.	176	25	60	175,6	230	172,6
7.	172,6	25	59	171,3	260	167,7
8.	167,7	25	62	166,7	230	163,7
9.	163,7	30	65	162,3	255	158,8
10.	158,8	25	62	157,6	250	154,8
11.	154,8	25	59	153	240	150,8
12.	150,8	25	60	148,9	220	146
13.	146	25	61	144	230	142
14.	142	25	62	139	235	137
15.	137	25	61	134	230	131,9
16.	131,9	25	61	129	236	126,5
17.	126,9	25	62	125	230	121,7
18.	121,7	27	63	118	250	113,6
19.	113,6	26	62	110,9	253	107,3
20.		503			4171	

Conclusion: The article suggests that drying cinnamon root using ultra-high frequency waves has significant advantages over infrared drying and other drying methods. Microwave drying has the potential to save energy due to the short duration of the process, the rapid drying time in the raw material, and the short energy delivery time.

It took 4674 seconds (80 minutes) to dry 200 grams of candy beans in a microwave dryer with 51.69% moisture content, of which 503 seconds were spent on power supply and 4171 seconds were spent on cooling, which consumed no energy. It took 14,400 seconds (240 minutes) to dry 200 grams of candy root with the same initial moisture in an infrared dryer. The dryer worked continuously during this period.

The roots of the candy, dried in both ways, did not differ in appearance. The dried samples were analyzed using high-performance liquid chromatography to determine quality parameters. According to the results of the analysis, the glycyrrhizic acid content of the sample dried in a

microwave oven was 5.92%, and the glycyrrhizic acid content of the sample dried in an infrared dryer was 4.83%.

So the conclusion is that microwave drying is much more effective than other methods in extending the shelf life of candy root.

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